

Measurement of Stability Constant and Some Thermodynamic Parameters of Clay Humus System

M. ADHIKARI* and T. K. MUKHOPADHYAY

Physical Chemistry Laboratory, Department of Applied Chemistry, University of Calcutta

Manuscript received 23 February 1979, revised 12 December 1979, accepted 18 March 1980

Stability constants of clay humus complexes are evaluated by an analytical method based on a new approach, and the thermodynamic functions of the products are calculated. The values of the latter indicate the spontaneity of the reaction. The entropy change (ΔS) for clay humus interactions are positive and are moderately high, indicating the chelation phenomena of clay—organic matter interaction as purely an entropy effect.

ALTHOUGH a number of studies¹⁻³ are reported regarding the nature and relative stability of the products formed by the reaction of metals with humic materials, very little attempt has yet been made to evaluate these in case of clay—humus interaction⁴.

This paper reports the determination of a new method to calculate the stability constant values of clay humus interaction products and to derive some thermodynamic parameters in order to get an idea regarding the nature of such interactions in the environment.

Theory :

According to Martell and Calvin⁵, the equilibrium reaction for chelation or complex formation can be written as

where 'M' is the metal ion and 'K_s' is the complexing agent and 'n' the number of moles of the complexing agent that combine with one mol of 'M'. Therefore, the formation constant or equilibrium constant can be expressed as

$$K = \frac{[M(K_s)_n]_{eq}}{[M]_{eq} [K_s]_{eq}^n} \quad \dots (2)$$

where $[M]_{eq}$ = Equilibrium concentration.

The calculation of concentrations of unreacted H—Clay and unreacted HA (or FA) are based on the assumption that H-Clay and HA(or FA) in the complexes are so strongly bound that during continuous neutralisation with dilute alkali, the complexes do not suffer any dissociation but only the unreacted H-Clay and HA (or FA) react with alkali.

Let the volume of alkali in ml required to neutralise the unreacted H-Clay and HA(or FA) after complexation = V_1 ... (3)

Let the volume of alkali in ml required to neutralise the total amount of HA(or FA) added for complexation) = V_2 ... (4)

and let the volume of alkali required in ml to neutralise the total amount of H-Clay used for the complexation = V_3 ... (5)

i.e., the total amount of alkali in ml required for both the H-Clay and HA(or FA) when there is no complexation = $V_2 + V_3$

Therefore, the amount of alkali in ml. which is not required when there is complexation between H-Clay and HA(or FA) : $V_4 = [(V_2 + V_3) - V_1]$

The pK_a values of H-Clay and HA(or FA) can be determined from the volumes of alkali required at the half neutralisation point. Knowing the pK_a values of H-Clay and HA(or FA), the relative strength of H-Clay and HA(or FA) species in the reaction system may be evaluated. Since the relative strength of an acid is a measure of its tendency to release the proton, the position of the equilibrium with a given solvent, as determined by the dissociation constant, is an indication of the strength of the acid. Let the ratio of the relative strengths of H-Clay and HA(or FA) be 'Z', then the volume of alkali in ml required for H-Clay (unreacted)

$$= \frac{V_1 \times Z}{1 + Z} \quad \dots (6)$$

and the volume of alkali in ml required for HA(or FA) (unreacted)

$$= \frac{V_1 \times 1}{1 + Z} \quad \dots (7)$$

If the average molecular weight and the colloid content of H-Clay and the HA (or FA) are known, then with the help of equations (1), (2) and (3), it is possible to

*Present address : College of Agriculture, Calcutta University.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR H-CLAY - HA(OR FA) COMPLEXES

H-Clay and HA(or FA) complexes in molar ratio	(T ± 0.5) A	-ΔG × 10 ³ kJ. mol ⁻¹	ΔH × 10 ³ kJ. mol ⁻¹	ΔS × 10 ³ kJ. mol ⁻¹ A ⁻¹
Original H-Clay - HA(1:5)	283	5.2295	3.0230	.29160
	303	5.8127		
Oxide free H-Clay - HA(1:42.5)	283	4.9244	2.5946	.26568
	303	5.4558		
Original H-Clay - FA(1:12)	283	4.2033	10.4730	.51859
	303	5.2405		
Oxide free H-Clay - FA(1:60)	283	4.0797	6.2195	.36392
	303	4.8076		

Discussion

The higher value of the stability constant (vide Table 1) of original H-Clay—HA complex than that for original H-Clay—FA system indicates a greater stability of the former. The removal of the sesquioxides coating decreases the stability constant value, which suggests the greater complexing ability of the sesquioxides groups. The stability constant values for the complexes increase with increase in temperature. This is due to partial removal of hydrated water molecules from the clay surfaces with rise in temperature, which makes available more of complexing sites to the clay surfaces for interaction.

The values of free energy (ΔG)—, enthalpy (ΔH)—, and entropy (ΔS)—changes for different clay—organic matter interaction products are given in Table 2. A comparison of these results reveals that the free energies of formation of the complexes are negative in all the cases, indicating the process of interaction to be spontaneous. The values of ΔH in all the cases (vide Table 2) are positive, indicating an absorption of energy during interactions. ΔH has been calculated (equation 11) by assuming it to remain constant over a temperature range from 10° to 30° for a given complexation process (e. g., that between original H-Clay and FA or oxide free H-Clay and HA etc.), although such ΔH values are obviously different for different complexation processes over the same range of temperatures.

The entropy changes (ΔS), accompanying the formation of complexes, are positive and greater than ΔH (which are also positive) in all the cases; this goes to emphasise that such chelation reaction is an "entropy—controlled" effect. The moderately high values of ΔS indicate the strong complexing ability of humic materials towards clays. The values of the stability constant and the thermodynamic parameters

are less for oxide free H-Clay—HA(or FA) species in incomparision with those for the original H-Clay. This is due to a high bonding ability of the sesquioxides coatings of clays with the humic fractions.

From the more or less similar values of the thermodynamic parameters for different soil humus species, it appears that the nature and the stereochemistry of the different functional groups of the legands taking part in such complexations, are almost identical. This corroborates the earlier findings by Infrared spectral study of Clay humus systems.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (T. K. M.) is thankful to C. S. I. R., New Delhi, for the award of a Post Doctoral Fellowship.

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